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HONEY BEE GENETICS

Genetica di Apis mellifera

When we consider the discovery that drones arise from unfertilised eggs (DZIERZON, 1845), we recognise that honey bee genetics has a history that is older than the Laws of Mendel. Dzierzon went on to introduce Italian bees to his home apiary, and disturbed the yellow bees to many parts of Europe and even to the USA. In other words, humans have been producing hybrid honey bees for more than 150 years. That this is still considered an accepted breeding concept up until this day, is an indication of the difficulties we have in front of us, when trying to convince beekeepers to protect local honey bee genetic diversity.

Many modern beekeepers insist that hybrid bees are better. Frequently beekeepers quote a book from BROTHER ADAM (1982), that cites his experience for the many crossed between the so-called Buckfast bees and numerous natural subspecies of honey bees. Examining the work of Brother Adam deeper, it is clear that it is a huge collection of anecdotes, however, it is of limited scientific value. It seems timely to ask, if the bees from Buckfast abbey have gained such a popular following, in spite of the fallacies in genetic theory in the Buckfast concept.

The fact that we still have natural populations of honey bees all across Europe, points to the rather limited influence human breeding activities has had on the species. There seem two possible explanations for the resilience of honey bees towards genetic manipulation. Either our tools have been rather too poor and the efforts being put into the endeavour have often been in vain, or honey bees' adaptations to their natural

environment are more significant than the minor alterations created by humanity.

Following the second world war, Ruttner in Germany took up the challenge to improve their honey bee population. With support from beekeepers, breeding organisation and local governments in Germany, the work eventually resulted in the eradication of the local population of *Apis mellifera mellifera*, which is now, by and large replaced by *A. m. carnica* bees (RUTTNER, 1983). This appears the only well documented example of a near complete take-over, and 50 years of work was needed to exclude the last bits of influence from the natural populations of honey bees (TIESSLER *et al.*, 2016).

The importance of being well adapted is illustrated by the bees from Malta. In spite of a long history of introductions of foreign bees, the tiny population on Malta still contains pure honey bees from the local subspecies of *A. m. ruttneri* (ZAMMIT-MANGION *et al.*, 2017) Introduced bees may well struggle both with the warm climate and the wasp, *Vespa orientalis*.

We are still lacking evidence of the consequences for local bees, when locally adapted queens are mating with a mixture of local and introduced drones. The rarity of hybrid colonies in the huge study on the Iberian Peninsula (CHÁVES-GALARZA *et al.*, 2013), could suggest that in fact the burden of carrying introduced genes, results in such colonies perishing quickly. The high loss rates often reported in modern beekeeping, could well result from the admixture of many subspecies, and as such should be seen as a purging of maladapted genes. It is possible that a genomic incompatibility exists, that prevents hybrids in becoming established, for instance as reported for the bees on Mount Kenya (WALLBERG *et al.*, 2017) where chromosomal rearrangements seem to form a barrier against genetic exchange.

REFERENCES

- BROTHER ADAM, 1982. Züchtung der Honigbiene. *Delta Verlag*, Sankt Augustin, Germany.
- CHÁVES-GALARZA J., HENRIQUES D., JOHNSTON J.S., AZAVEDO J.C., PATTON J.C., MUNOZ I., DE LA RÚA P. & PINTO M.A., 2013. Signatures of selection in the Iberian honey bee (*Apis mellifera iberiensis*) revealed by a genome scan analysis of single nucleotide polymorphisms. *Mol. Ecol.*, 22(23): 5890-5907.
- DZIERZON J., 1845. Gutachten über die von Herrn Direktor Stöhr im ersten und zweiten Kapitel des General-Gutachtens aufgestellten Fragen. *Eickstädter Bienez.*, 1: 109-113, 119-121-
- RUTTNER F., 1983. Zuchttechnik und Zuchtauslese bei der Biene. *Ehrenwirth Verlag*, München, Germany.
- TIESSLER K.-F., BIENEFELD K. & BÜCHLER R., 2016. Selektion bei der Honigbiene. *Buschhausen Druck und Verlaghaus*, Herten, Germany.
- WALLBERG A., SCHOENING C., WEBSTER M.T. & HASSELMANN M., 2017. Two extended haplotypes

blocks are associated with adaptation to high altitude habitats in East African honey bees. *PLoS Genetics*, 13(5): e1006792.

ZAMMIT-MANGION M., MEIXNER M., MIFSUD D., SAMMUT S. & CAMILLERI L., 2017. Thorough morphological and genetic evidence confirm the existence of the endemic honey bee of the Maltese Islands *Apis mellifera ruttneri*: Recommendations for conservation. *J. Apicult. Res.*, 56(5): 514-522.

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